

TRENDS OF BREEDING BIRDS IN THE WADDEN SEA 1991-2023

AND RESULTS OF THE
TOTAL COUNT IN 2018

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Common Redshank. Photo by Benjamin Gnep

SUMMARY

Sandwich Terns. Photo by Florian Pecknor.

This report summarises trends and numbers of coastal breeding birds in the transboundary Wadden Sea. It is an update of the last report from 2020, adding another six years to the existing data series. Hence, we can report on long-term trends in changes in abundance (since 1991, i.e. 33 years) and short-term trends for the last twelve years (2012-2023).

In addition, information on population size is added, based on total counts of all breeding birds which are carried out once every six years. Data presented here have been collected in the framework of the Trilateral Monitoring and Assessment Programme (TMAP), coordinated by the Expert Group Breeding Birds of the Trilateral Cooperation. Data collection is carried out by a large number of volunteer and professional bird counters, locally supported by various agencies and institutions in the respective countries (or federal states in Germany).

Trend calculations are carried out by Statistics Netherlands (CBS), based on data stored in a new and dedicated database, hosted by Sovon Vogelonderzoek Nederland in the Netherlands. The results are presented as an overall

overview, aiming to give quick access to the most important findings (chapter 3) and an account on a selection of species, presenting the data in more detail (i.e. country-level), along with a short text to give context to the observed changes in abundance (chapter 4).

Over the long term, most breeding bird species in the Wadden Sea are in decline. For the period 1991-2023, 19 out of 31 species (61%) for which trends could be calculated have been subject to significant decreases.

For the last twelve seasons, many uncertain trends dominate, as the period of twelve years and annual fluctuations result in many non-significant trends (the power of trend calculations is less compared to long term trends). Still, also for the recent period, eleven out of 31 species (36% at trilateral level) have shown decreases while only five have increased in numbers.

Increasing species are mainly some colonial breeding birds that often have shown increases on a much wider geographical scale in Northwest-Europe. Examples of such species are Barnacle Goose, Eurasian Spoonbill, Great Black-backed Gull and Great Cormorant.

On the other hand, a whole series of typical Wadden Sea breeding birds like Arctic Tern, Common Redshank, Common Tern, Eurasian Oystercatcher and Pied Avocet have shown declines, which in many species have persisted into the recent twelve-year period.

Obvious differences between long- and short-term trends for the transboundary Wadden Sea show that some formerly thriving species have slowed down their population growth (Eurasian Spoonbill), have stabilised (Barnacle Goose) or are now even in decline (Lesser Black-backed Gull). In addition stable long-term numbers in a species like Common Shelduck have now turned into a decline and declines reported in Common Gull have accelerated recently. On the other hand, some long-term declining species seem to have stabilised at a lower population level more recently (Common Redshank, Northern Lapwing) or even show signs of recent recovery (Common Eider).

Previous reports of the Trilateral Wadden Sea Cooperation have highlighted multiple times the large number of breeding bird species that are subject to declines and the addition

of recent census data in this report show that the overall negative balance of species' fortunes has remained in recent years. Moreover, in the Netherlands and Lower Saxony/ Hamburg there are more declining species compared to Schleswig-Holstein and Denmark.

Causes for the declines may be multi-factorial, e.g. losses by high predation rates (especially along the mainland coast, locally also islands, notably by Brown rat), losses by high tides during the breeding season and limited food resources. These aspects are discussed in the species accounts, without going into much detail, since trilateral progress reports like this aim to provide baseline trends and other information about (observed changes in) abundance but do not aim to provide an in-depth background analysis of the observed population changes for each species.

Common Redshank. Photo by Benjamin Gneip

Arctic Terns. Photo by Christian Wiedemann

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1. INTRODUCTION

1. INTRODUCTION

The Wadden Sea World Heritage Site is well-known as a stop-over, moulting or wintering site for many migratory bird species (e.g. Kleefstra et al. 2025), but it is also an important breeding area for coastal breeding bird species like Common Shelduck, Eurasian Oystercatcher, Pied Avocet, Common Redshank, Lesser Black-backed Gull, Sandwich Tern and Common Tern. For breeding Eurasian Spoonbill and Gull-billed Tern, the Wadden Sea is even the most important stronghold in Northwest-Europe.

Surveys of coastal breeding birds have been carried out since 1991 within the framework of the Trilateral Monitoring and Assessment Programme (TMAP). They cover the entire tidal ecosystem stretching from Den Helder in the Netherlands to Esbjerg in Denmark.

Additionally, they also include breeding sites behind the seawall, like dunes, polders and coastal wetlands (often referred to as the Wadden Sea Cooperation area). Data from national survey schemes, harmonised at trilateral level, are collated and published in periodical progress reports to inform policy makers, site managers, researchers and participants in the counts

(e.g. Koffijberg et al. 2020). Data from these progress reports also feed into the periodical Quality Status Reports, in which breeding birds constitute one of the thematic reports (Koffijberg et al. 2022).

This progress report provides an update of the trends in breeding bird numbers in the Wadden Sea up to 2023 and presents an overview of the results of the total count in 2018. The last progress report included data until 2017 (Koffijberg et al. 2020). The main part (chapter 4) of this report consists of species accounts in which the results for each breeding bird species are shortly summarised and explained. Trilateral progress reports provide baseline trends and other information about (observed changes in) abundance of breeding birds but they do not aim to provide in-depth analysis of the drivers of the observed population changes.

Breeding bird counters during fieldwork. Photo by Benjamin Gnep

2. DATA AND METHODS

2. DATA AND METHODS

TMAP-breeding bird data are collected according to two census strategies (Tab. 2.1). The methods and the collation of data are coordinated by the trilateral Expert Group Breeding Birds. Colonial and rare breeding bird species (27 species) are counted annually, aiming for full coverage of all breeding sites each year. Besides, common breeding birds (8 species) are surveyed annually at a selection of census sites, under the assumption that data from these sites mirror overall trends in numbers for the different sections within the Wadden Sea.

Once every six years, all 35 species are covered in a so-called total count, which aims to achieve an overview of abundance and distribution of all coastal breeding bird species. Results of these total counts are also used to adjust overall trends in common breeding birds, and to account for differences in abundance throughout the Wadden Sea.

Fieldwork is based on a trilateral manual with guidelines for census methods (Hälterlein 1995) with national adjustments connected to national monitoring requirements (e.g. Vergeer et al. 2023 for the Netherlands,

	Numbers, distribution and trends in numbers since 1991		Breeding success since 2010	Contaminants in bird eggs since 1998
Species monitored	27 rare and colonial breeders	8 common breeders: Common Shelduck, Common Eider, Eurasian Oystercatcher, Common Ringed Plover, Northern Lapwing, Black-tailed Godwit, Eurasian Curlew, Common Redshank	Selection of 10 representative species	Selection of 2 representative species
Count strategy	Total count annually	Count in census areas annually, total count once every six (formerly five) years: 1991, 1996, 2001, 2006, 2012, 2018, 2024	Sample sites annually	Sample sites annually

Table 2.1. Set up of the TMAP monitoring scheme for breeding birds. This report presents data on numbers, distribution and trends since 1991 whereas breeding success and contaminants in bird eggs are published separately.

Südbeck et al. 2025 for Germany). Data may be collected by a one-off count at the most optimal time of the breeding period or is based on multiple counts during the breeding season, from which numbers of territories or breeding pairs are derived (note that breeding pairs and territories are throughout this report referred to as breeding pairs). At present, much field data is processed by using technical devices and apps during fieldwork (e.g. Avimap in the Netherlands, QField app in Schleswig-Holstein), which add to the standardisation during data collection and facilitate easy workflows in data-processing. After the breeding season, all data is collated by the national coordinator in each section of the Wadden Sea (i.e. the Netherlands, Lower Saxony, Hamburg, Schleswig-Holstein and Denmark), checked and validated before submission to the trilateral database. The latest national accounts on breeding birds from the Wadden Sea have been given by Thorup et al. (2021) (Denmark), Mitschke et al. 2024 (Lower Saxony/Hamburg) and Boele et al. 2025 (the Netherlands). These national reports also provide more details about data collection and data processing in the individual countries.

Compared to previous progress reports, a major change has been made in database management. Since 2024, all breeding bird data, both numbers and breeding success, are managed in a dedicated (online) PostgreS database at Sovon Vogelonderzoek Nederland in Nijmegen, the Netherlands. This facilitates the trend calculations which are carried out by Statistics Netherlands (CBS), by using the same routines that have been established in the Dutch breeding bird monitoring scheme (Boele et al. 2025).

In conjunction with this change in data management and in preparation of this progress report, existing data for Denmark and Schleswig-Holstein have been completely replaced by new datasets, including a general screening of data for Schleswig-Holstein and some validation checks on Danish data. As a result, numbers and trends in some species may slightly deviate of those published in previous progress reports. In addition, also data from the Lower Elbe in Lower Saxony have undergone some corrections, affecting specifically trends of Common Gull and Mediterranean Gull, which now have been corrected with this report (earlier reports included data from outside the Wadden Sea Cooperation area).

Eurasian Spoonbill. Photo by Benjamin Gnep

For trend calculations, the Wadden Sea is divided in seven smaller units, i.e. (1) western Wadden Sea, (2) eastern Wadden Sea (the Netherlands), (3) Ems-Dollart Estuary (the Netherlands and Lower Saxony), (4) East-Frisian Coast (Lower Saxony), (5) Weser-Elbe Estuary (Lower Saxony, Hamburg and Schleswig-Holstein), (6) North Frisian Wadden Sea (Schleswig-Holstein) and (7) Danish Wadden Sea. The delineation of these regions has been made according to the existing so-called TMAP regions 1-56 which are used in the TMAP breeding bird monitoring and also represent the unit in which distribution maps are presented (see chapter 4).

Trends have been calculated with rTRIM (Boogaart et al. 2016), which is now widely used for estimating population dynamics in bird numbers in Europe. Before starting trend calculations, multiple validation routines are applied to the submitted data to check for any inconsistencies. Working with rTRIM also includes estimates for missing counts, e.g. because a site was not covered in a certain year, and it thus provides a full dataset that is not influenced by gaps in coverage. The trends in the seven regions are

aggregated to trends for the Netherlands, Lower Saxony/Hamburg, Schleswig-Holstein and Denmark (in case of the shared estuaries, data of counting sites are used according to the administrative borders, so e.g. for the Netherlands, only the Dutch part of Ems-Dollart Estuary is used for the trend of the Dutch part of the Wadden Sea). These country-specific trends constitute the backbone of data presentations in chapter 4. Trends in common species are weighted for the share of the total population in each region (based on results of the total counts), to account for differences in the number of census sites between the regions within the Wadden Sea. Trends in numbers are presented for the entire period 1991-2023 (long term) and for the last twelve years, i.e. 2012-2023 (short term). All trend classifications in this report follow the scheme presented in Tab. 2.2, in line with the previous progress reports.

New to previous reports is, that counting units have been assigned to mainland or island, in order to allow calculation of trends in numbers along the mainland coast versus the islands. In this report these are only presented for the

entire Wadden Sea. The main trigger for this additional trend assessment is the difference in predation risk from mammalian predators, which has been identified as a main driver for current population changes (e.g. Koffijberg et al. 2016, Leyrer et al. 2019). On most islands, mammalian predators do not occur naturally but at some islands their presence

has been facilitated by man, either by direct introduction or by connecting the islands to the mainland by dams. In the analyses, all islands have been merged, regardless of their connectivity with the mainland coast. In the context of discussions about predation management, a comparison of trends between islands and mainland may assist

in identification of drivers for population change and subsequent management measures. They are only presented in chapter 4 for the relevant species, i.e. in species which predominantly breed either on islands or mainland, the comparison is omitted. Further refinement may be done in next editions of progress reports.

Trend classification	Trend description	Trend explanation
	strong increase	significant increase of > 5% per year
	moderate increase	significant increase of < 5% per year
	stable	no significant population change detectable
	moderate decrease	significant decrease of < 5% per year
	strong decrease	significant decrease of > 5% per year
	uncertain	no reliable trend classification possible, mostly due to strongly fluctuating numbers during 12-year period

Table 2.2. Trend classifications for changes in breeding bird numbers used in this report (and in previous progress reports as well).

3. OVERVIEW NUMBERS AND TRENDS

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In order to allow a quick overview of the changes in numbers of breeding pairs, Table 3.1 summarises trends for each species in the four entities within the Wadden Sea (the Netherlands, Lower Saxony/Hamburg, Schleswig-Holstein, Denmark) as well as the entire transboundary Wadden Sea. They are shown for both the entire period 1991-2023 and the short-term period 2012-2023 (i.e. the last twelve years). At first sight, it becomes obvious that over the long term, most breeding bird species are in decline.

For the transboundary Wadden Sea in 1991-2023, 19 out of 31 species (61%) for which trends could be calculated are subject to significant decreases (Fig. 3.1, 3.2).

Table 3.1. Long- and short term trends in breeding birds in the Wadden Sea countries, WS Wadden Sea, DK Denmark, SH Schleswig-Holstein, LS/HH Lower Saxony and Hamburg, NL the Netherlands.

Note that extremely rare species have not been included (Eurasian Wigeon, Northern Pintail, Little Gull, Ruddy Turnstone). When cells have been left blank, a trend calculation for the combination of species and country was not possible (species does not occur at all in this part of the Wadden Sea, or only in very small numbers). WS Wadden Sea, DK Denmark, SH Schleswig-Holstein, LS/HH Lower Saxony and Hamburg, NL the Netherlands. Trends are according to the scheme in Tab. 2.2.

Species	Long-term 33-years trend 1991-2023					Short-term 12-years trend 2012-2023				
	WS	DK	SH	LS/HH	NL	WS	DK	SH	LS/HH	NL
Great Cormorant	↑	---	↑↑	↑	---	↑	---	↓	---	↑
Little Egret	---				↑	---				---
Eurasian Spoonbill	↑↑	---	---	↑↑	↑↑	↑	---	↑↑	↑	---
Barnacle Goose	↑↑	---	---	---	↑↑	---	---	↓	---	↑↑
Common Shelduck	---	---	---	↑	---	↓	---	↓	---	↓
Common Eider	↓	↑	↓	↑	↓	↑	---	---	↑	---
Red-breasted Merganser	↑	---	↑	---	↓	---	---	↑	---	---
Hen Harrier	↓↓			↓↓	↓↓	---			---	---
Eurasian Oystercatcher	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	---	↓	---
Pied Avocet	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	---	---	↓	---
Common Ringed Plover	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	---	---	---	---	---
Kentish Plover	↓	↑	---	↓↓	↓↓	---	↑	---	---	---
Nothern Lapwing	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	---	---	---	---	↓
Dunlin	↓↓					↓↓				
Ruff	↓					↓				
Common Snipe	↓↓					---				
Black-tailed Godwit	↓	↓	---	↓	↓	---	---	---	---	↓
Eurasian Curlew	↓	---		---	↓	↓	---		---	↓
Common Redshank	↓	↓	---	↓	↓	---	---	---	---	---
Mediterranean Gull	---		↑	↑↑	↑	---		---	↑	---
Common Black-headed Gull	↓	↑	---	↓	↓	---	---	---	---	↓
Common Gull	↓	↓	↑	↑	↓	↓↓	↓↓	---	↓↓	↓
Lesser Black-backed Gull	↑	↑↑	↑	↑	↑	↓	↓↓	↓	---	↓
Herring Gull	↓	↑	↓	↓	↓	↓	---	---	---	↓
Great Black-backed Gull	↑↑	↑	↑↑	↑	---	↑↑	---	↑↑	↑	↑↑
Gull-billed Tern	---		↑			---		---		
Sandwich Tern	---	---	↓	---	---	---	---	↑	---	---
Common Tern	↓	---	---	↓	↓	---	---	---	---	---
Arctic Tern	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	---	---	---	↓
Little Tern	↑	---	↓	↓	↑	↑	↑	---	---	↑
Short-eared Owl	↓			↓	↓	↓			---	↓

For a better overview, moderate and strong population changes (cf. Tab. 3.1) have been aggregated to one level in Figure 3.1a and 3.1b. Note that in 2012-2023 in many species no significant population changes could be detected, since the period is rather short (12 years) and annual fluctuations easily lead to non-significant (i.e. uncertain) trends. Species accounts in chapter 4 give more details.

Number of species / Area

Figure 3.1a. Long-term (1991-2023) trends for breeding birds in the Wadden Sea.

Number of species / Area

Figure 3.1b. Short-term (2012-2023) trends for breeding birds in the Wadden Sea.

For the last twelve seasons, many uncertain trends dominate, as the period of twelve years and annual fluctuations result in many non-significant trends (the power of trend calculations is less compared to long-term trends). Still, also for the recent period, eleven out of 31 species (36% at trilateral level) show decreases while only five have increased in numbers. Increasing species are mainly some colonial breeding birds that often have shown increases

on a much wider geographical scale in Northwest-Europe, such as Barnacle Goose, Eurasian Spoonbill, Great Black-backed Gull and Great Cormorant. On the other hand, a whole series of typical Wadden Sea breeding birds like Arctic Tern, Common Redshank, Common Tern, Eurasian Oystercatcher and Pied Avocet have shown declines, which in many species have persisted into the recent twelve-year period. Obvious differences between long-

and short-term trends for the transboundary Wadden Sea show that some formerly thriving species have slowed down their population growth (Eurasian Spoonbill), have stabilised (Barnacle Goose) or are now even in decline (Lesser Black-backed Gull). In addition, stable long-term numbers in a species like Common Shelduck have now turned into a decline and declines reported in Common Gull have accelerated recently. On the other hand, some long-term

declining species seem to have stabilised at a lower population level more recently (Common Redshank, Northern Lapwing) or even show signs of recent recovery (Common Eider).

The general picture of declines dominating among coastal breeding birds in the transboundary Wadden Sea are mirrored well by the situation in the Netherlands and Lower Saxony/Hamburg, i.e. west of the river Elbe (Fig. 3.1).

Long-term downward trends in the Netherlands are found in 17 out of 27 species (63%) and in Lower Saxony/Hamburg in 14 out of 26 species (54%). In Schleswig-Holstein and Denmark, the relative share of long-term declining species is much lower, 38% and 32% respectively. Obvious contrasting trends (in the context of overall decreases) in those two parts of the Wadden Sea include increasing/stable trends in Black-headed Gull, Common Tern and Kentish Plovers and stable trends in Common Redshank (only Schleswig-Holstein) (Tab. 3.1). A more in-depth analysis of such contrasting trends potentially could reveal background drivers for such diverging trends, for instance related to site management, food resources (also in relation to e.g. nutrient input or climatological aspects) and differences in predation risk.

Previous reports have highlighted multiple times the large number of breeding bird species that are subject to declines, and the addition of data from 2017-2023 in this report show that the overall balance of species' fortunes remains the same. Actually, the number of decreasing species has grown in time while thriving species more or less remained the same (Fig. 3.3).

Figure 3.2. Summary of trends in breeding birds in the Wadden Sea 1991-2023, expressed as the rate of mean annual population change (in %), ranked from increasing species (top, right) to decreasing species (bottom, left). Green: species with significant increases; orange: no significant trend detectable; red: significant decline; grey: trend uncertain (cf. Tab. 2.2).

Figure 3.3. Summary of trends in QSR-context. Trends presented in this report are compared with previous assessments in Quality Status Reports (latest on breeding birds being 2021, see Koffijberg et al. 2022).

Table 3.2 gives an overview of the numbers counted during the last total count in 2018 (previous total counts given for comparison). Total counts aim to provide a snapshot of distribution and overall numbers once every six years, to keep track on the overall abundance of coastal breeding birds in the Wadden Sea. Over all species together, 319,000 breeding pairs (rounded) were counted, which is a loss of about 19% compared to the 395,000 pairs counted in 2012 (395,500 in 2006, see Koffijberg et al. 2020 for details).

In terms of total number of breeding pairs, most abundant species in 2018 include some colonial breeding birds (Common Black-headed Gull, Lesser Black-backed Gull, Herring Gull) or species that occur in higher densities all over the Wadden Sea (e.g. Eurasian Oystercatcher, Northern Lapwing).

Among the rarest species (less than ten breeding pairs) are Little Egret, Hen Harrier and Dunlin; Ruddy Turnstone and Little Gull were not found at all in 2018. Especially the small numbers of Dunlin represent an important conservation issue, as they represent the small and declining subspecies (*schinzii*) breeding in Europe. Hen Harrier has undergone a decline in numbers and the small remnant population seems on the brink of extinction (see species account in next chapter) whereas Little Egret is a new breeding species for the Wadden Sea and may expand in future.

Species	1991	1996	2001	2006	2012	2018
Great Cormorant	312	838	2,475	3,666	4,873	5,007
Little Egret	-	-	-	14	4	7
Eurasian Spoonbill	216	484	724	1,215	1,945	2,757
Barnacle Goose	-	-	-	236	727	1,297
Common Shelduck	4,413 ¹	4,982	6,480	6,582	7,431	6,332
Common Eider	8,408	11,534	10,497	8,981	7,283	5,282
Red-breasted Merganser	15	41	44	42	41	72
Hen Harrier	124	142	167	89	21	6
Eurasian Oystercatcher	37,156 ¹	46,591	39,927	30,476	26,313	28,694
Pied Avocet	11,844	11,214	12,389	10,827	7,179	6,700
Common Ringed Plover	1,364 ¹	1,367	1,093	688	658	777
Kentish Plover	569 ¹	521	330	282	291	435
Northern Lapwing	8,753 ¹	12,521	11,643	12,650	10,834	11,194
Dunlin	51	39	23	24	13	8
Ruff	242	82	35	46	39	41
Common Snipe	529 ¹	646	181	291	55	110
Black-tailed Godwit	2,117 ¹	3,004	2,824	2,513	2,351	2,160
Eurasian Curlew	782	632	640	611	515	355
Common Redshank	12,081 ¹	16,197	14,046	12,383	10,373	12,537
Ruddy Turnstone	3	2	1	0	1	0
Mediterranean Gull	2	5	45	183	137	35
Little Gull	2	2	0	0	2	0
Common Black-headed Gull	128,317	133,313	157,371	98,006	113,723	83,071
Common Gull	6,671	10,481	16,309	15,233	13,011	8,773
Lesser Black-backed Gull	18,016	38,252	79,013	88,623	94,496	71,838
Herring Gull	89,522	74,551	78,845	60,655	62,278	42,526
Great Black-backed Gull	6	15	33	35	72	171
Gull-billed Tern	28	86	60	45	40	37
Sandwich Tern	16,982	17,285	17,170	22,398	15,779	16,035
Common Tern	13,677	13,064	14,224	10,511	8,442	7,198
Arctic Tern	5,256 ¹	9,011	8,725	5,459	4,849	4,325
Little Tern	654 ¹	983	1,099	708	760	1,052
Short-eared Owl	83	114	103	75	68	32

Table 3.2. Status of breeding birds (number of breeding pairs) in the Wadden Sea during total counts in 1991, 1996, 2001, 2006, 2012 and 2018. Little Egret and Barnacle Geese were first implemented in 2006 in TMAP, so only data presented for 2006 and later. Eurasian Wigeon and Northern Pintail not listed as data series very incomplete (but see Tab. 3.3 for 2018). See also the previous report (Koffijberg et al. 2020) for full account on data sources.

¹ incomplete coverage in Denmark, inland grassland areas and sandy beaches not covered.

Species	Denmark	Schleswig-Holstein	Lower Saxony/Hamburg	The Netherlands
Great Cormorant	6	968	785	3,248
Little Egret	0	0	0	7
Eurasian Spoonbill	45	343	657	1,712
Barnacle Goose	3	558	367	369
Common Shelduck	160	2,772	2,299	1,101
Eurasian Wigeon	0	35	0	2
Northern Pintail	1	16	2	4
Common Eider	359	461	1,229	3,233
Red-breasted Merganser	0	66	5	1
Hen Harrier	0	(0)	2	4
Eurasian Oystercatcher	1,248	12,688	7,153	7,605
Pied Avocet	409	3,039	1,271	1,981
Common Ringed Plover	109	418	153	97
Kentish Plover	89	315	16	15
Northern Lapwing	2,059	4,398	2,218	2,519
Dunlin	7	0	1	0
Ruff	13	28	0	0
Common Snipe	85	5	15	5
Black-tailed Godwit	216	510	394	1,040
Eurasian Curlew	42	4	93	216
Common Redshank	1,570	4,311	3,854	2,802
Ruddy Turnstone	0	0	0	0
Mediterranean Gull	2	4	25	4
Little Gull	0	0	0	0
Common Black-headed Gull	9,072	24,876	19,513	29,610
Common Gull	569	3,186	3,147	1,871
Lesser Black-backed Gull	1,218	14,061	24,736	31,823
Herring Gull	8,242	7,759	9,780	16,745
Great Black-backed Gull	15	116	12	28
Gull-billed Tern	0	37	0	0
Sandwich Tern	154	2,935	4,742	8,204
Common Tern	89	2,248	2,051	2,810
Arctic Tern	504	2,214	737	870
Little Tern	140	233	209	470
Short-eared Owl	2	2	20	8

Table 3.3. Results of the total count 2018: number of breeding pairs per country. For Hen Harrier in Schleswig-Holstein, single breeding pairs may have been missed.

The different breeding bird species do not occur evenly distributed over the Wadden Sea, as is also shown in more detail in the species distribution maps in the next chapter. Apart from species that are widespread and whose numbers will strongly depend on the respective size of the Wadden Sea in each country, some species breed in large numbers in specific sections of the Wadden Sea.

In Denmark, important species (i.e. >50% of the entire Wadden Sea population breeding in this part of the Wadden Sea) are Dunlin and Common Snipe. Other species with high population shares include e.g. Kentish Plover, Northern Lapwing, Ruff and Herring Gull.

The Schleswig-Holstein Wadden Sea harbours the only colony of Gull-billed Tern in the Wadden Sea (and the whole rest of Northwest-Europe). Other important species here are Red-breasted Merganser, Common Ringed Plover, Kentish Plover, Ruff, Great Black-backed Gull and Arctic Tern (all >50% of the entire Wadden Sea population) as well as Barnacle Goose, Common Shelduck, Eurasian Oystercatcher, Pied Avocet,

Northern Lapwing, Common Redshank, Common Gull and Common Tern.

Lower Saxony and Hamburg support more than half of the breeding populations of Mediterranean Gull and Short-eared Owl, but also harbour larger numbers of e.g. Barnacle Goose, Common Shelduck, Hen Harrier, Common Redshank, Common Gull, Lesser Black-backed Gull, Sandwich Tern and Common Tern.

Little Egret is exclusively breeding in the Dutch part of the Wadden Sea. Other species with more than half of the Wadden Sea population in this part of the Wadden Sea are Great Cormorant, Eurasian Spoonbill, Common Eider, Hen Harrier, Eurasian Curlew and Sandwich Tern.

For Black-tailed Godwit, Common Black-headed Gull, Lesser Black-backed Gull, Herring Gull, Common Tern and Little Tern, more than one third of the Wadden Sea population breeds in the Netherlands.

Distribution patterns are explained in more detail in the species accounts in the next chapter.

4. SPECIES ACCOUNTS

4. SPECIES ACCOUNTS

This chapter provides an overview of the monitoring results for the most relevant (abundant) species. It contains maps, bar charts and trend graphs for each species, along with an explanatory text that highlights the most important observations and when possible also gives some context to the observed patterns and trends. Illustrations include:

- A distribution map, showing number of breeding pairs for each of the 56 TMAP regions. These numbers are the results of the latest total count in 2018. Note that the position of the dots represent the midpoint coordinates of the respective TMAP region and not the precise location of the breeding site or colony.
- A bar chart showing total number of breeding birds in the Wadden Sea (all countries together) and numbers per country. Data is similar as in the distribution maps, referring to 2018. This bar chart gives insight how the breeding population is divided among the different countries within the Wadden Sea. (see also Tab. 3.3).
- Line graphs showing trends in numbers of breeding pairs per

country. Data is presented here as an index relative to (mostly) 1996. So this graph shows the changes in abundance, relative to this base year. Usually, five trend graphs have been included: one for the overall Wadden Sea and one for each country each. In some species with limited distribution, or too small numbers to calculate trends in a country, the graph is left empty and comes with a short explanation concerning data availability.

- Similar line graph as mentioned above, showing trends in abundance for mainland and islands (see chapter 2 for backgrounds). Note that the index as such only depicts the trend in numbers but does not indicate how many breeding pairs actually breed on islands and mainland respectively. If the index e.g. on islands is at a higher level than on the mainland, this does not indicate that more breeding pairs are found there.
- A table summarising trends per country, similar as Tab. 3.1 but now only for the particular species. Trend classification and symbols after Tab. 2.2.

Common Ringed Plovers. Photo by Benjamin Gnep

4.1 GREAT CORMORANT

00720 *Phalacrocorax carbo* Skarv / Kormoran / Aalscholver

Great Cormorant *Phalacrocorax carbo*

breeding pairs in the Wadden Sea in 2018

DENMARK

Schleswig-Holstein

GERMANY

Lower Saxony/
Hamburg

THE NETHERLANDS

Population size 2018: 5,007

Great Cormorants have been thriving in many parts of Northwest-Europe in the past decade and trends in the Wadden Sea reflect that development well. Both long- and short-term trends are pointing upwards, with a slightly slower rate of increase on the short term (on average +4% per year, compared to +6% per year for the long term).

Apart from a rather erratic trend in the Danish Wadden Sea (not shown), where the species is also subject to management measures (to prevent expansion), numbers in Schleswig-Holstein and Lower-Saxony/Hamburg have tended to stabilise or have even decreased significantly since 2012 (Schleswig-Holstein).

In the Netherlands they have continued to increase, despite a general decline in the country (Boele et al. 2025). Nearly all colonies are situated at islands or artificial offshore structures (platforms, etc.) and at some sites they also breed on the ground. Largest colonies are found in the western part of the Wadden Sea. ~~~

4.1 GREAT CORMORANT

Overall trend in the Wadden Sea

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

—●— Mainland ····· Island

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Trend summary: long term and short term

Area	1991-2023	2012-2023
Wadden Sea	↑	↑
Denmark	— —	— —
Schleswig-Holstein	↑↑	↓
Lower Saxony/Hamburg	↑	— —
The Netherlands	— —	↑

↑↑ strong increase ↑ moderate increase — stable
↓↓ strong decrease ↓ moderate decrease — — uncertain

No trend analysis available:
Species does not occur in this part of the Wadden Sea or is only an accidental breeder or occurs in very small numbers.

Denmark

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Schleswig-Holstein

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Total counts in the Wadden Sea per country in 2018

Number of breeding pairs / Area

Lower Saxony/Hamburg

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

The Netherlands

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

4.2 LITTLE EGRET

01190 *Egretta garzetta* Silkehejre / Seidenreiher / Kleine Zilverreiger

Little Egret *Egretta garzetta*

breeding pairs in the Wadden Sea in 2018

Population size 2018: 7

Little Egret is a species that has expanded its European breeding range to the north recently (Keller et al. 2020). Its northeastern edge just reaches into the westernmost part of the Wadden Sea, in the Netherlands.

Interestingly, breeding sites are currently mainly found in the eastern part of the Dutch part of the Wadden Sea, on the islands of Schiermonnikoog and Rottumeroog, but in nearby Lower Saxony, breeding has only occurred once (2007, Memmert). On a long term, total numbers have increased, but for the recent twelve years no significant trend could be detected. Initially numbers in the Dutch Wadden Sea steeply increased (Kleefstra et al. 2009), but this upward trend was disrupted in the cold winter of 2009/2010. Since then, they have never recovered and breeding has been reported in fluctuating numbers and on a much smaller scale.

Even an absence of cold winters since 2010 has not resulted in a recovery. Further expansion into the German or Danish parts of the Wadden Sea, as observed before in Eurasian Spoonbill, may perhaps be due in near future, as breeding numbers in the Netherlands in 2023 and 2024 showed signs of a major recovery (Boele et al. 2025).

4.2 LITTLE EGRET

Overall trend in the Wadden Sea

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

No trend analysis available:
Species does not occur in this part of the Wadden Sea or is only an accidental breeder or occurs in very small numbers.

Denmark

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

No trend analysis available:
Species does not occur in this part of the Wadden Sea or is only an accidental breeder or occurs in very small numbers.

Lower Saxony/Hamburg

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Schleswig-Holstein

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

The Netherlands

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Trend summary: long term and short term

Area	1991-2023	2012-2023
Wadden Sea	■ ■	■ ■
Denmark		
Schleswig-Holstein		
Lower Saxony/Hamburg		
The Netherlands	↑	■ ■

↑↑ strong increase ↑ moderate increase ■ stable
↓↓ strong decrease ↓ moderate decrease ■ ■ uncertain

Total counts in the Wadden Sea per country in 2018

Number of breeding pairs / Area

4.3 EURASIAN SPOONBILL

01440 *Platalea leucorodia* Skestork / Löffler / Lepelaar

Population size 2018: 2,757

In line with the numbers outside the breeding season, Eurasian Spoonbill has experienced a strong increase in all parts of the Wadden Sea since 1991, with an average plus of 8% per year (+6% per year since 2012). Since the expansion initially started in the Netherlands, highest numbers still breed west of the River Elbe. Schleswig-Holstein was colonised in 2000, Denmark followed 2007.

Apart from fluctuating numbers in Denmark, the species has continued to thrive in the German part of the Wadden Sea, notably in Schleswig-Holstein (+ 13% per year since 2012) whereas in the Dutch part of the Wadden Sea population growth has gradually levelled-off, resulting in a stable trend for the last twelve years. This stabilisation has been attributed to density-dependence, caused by food limitations (Oudman et al. 2017). It will be interesting to see future trends in Lower Saxony/ Hamburg and Schleswig-Holstein.

Colonies are mainly found in dune and salt marsh areas at the islands but feeding flocks can be found both in the intertidal area and in waterbodies behind the seawall. Incursions by predators (and perceived predation risk by the Spoonbills) may have profound impact on colony settlement and may lead to prolonged abandonment of colony sites, as was e.g. observed at Langli in Denmark.

4.3 EURASIAN SPOONBILL

Overall trend in the Wadden Sea

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Denmark

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Lower Saxony/Hamburg

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Schleswig-Holstein

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

The Netherlands

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Trend summary: long term and short term

Area	1991-2023	2012-2023
Wadden Sea	↑↑	↑
Denmark	—	—
Schleswig-Holstein	—	↑↑
Lower Saxony/Hamburg	↑↑	↑
The Netherlands	↑↑	▬

↑↑ strong increase ↑ moderate increase ▬ stable
 ↓↓ strong decrease ↓ moderate decrease — uncertain

Total counts in the Wadden Sea per country in 2018

Number of breeding pairs / Area

4.4 BARNACLE GOOSE

01670 *Branta leucopsis* Bramgås / Weißwangengans / Brandgans

Barnacle Goose *Branta leucopsis*

breeding pairs in the Wadden Sea in 2018

Population size 2018: 1,297

Barnacle Goose is a rather recent addition to the breeding birds in the Wadden Sea, following expansions in its temperate breeding range. Largest numbers in the Wadden Sea occur in Schleswig-Holstein, Lower Saxony and in the Netherlands, mainly on the islands (e.g. Föhr in Schleswig-Holstein and Texel and Terschelling in the Netherlands) and in the estuaries (e.g. islands within the River Ems in Lower Saxony).

Coverage of the counts is not complete and separation of breeding pairs and non-breeders may trouble precise counts. These may confound some of the trends shown here, especially for Schleswig-Holstein and Lower Saxony. On a long term there has been a general increase, in line with the expansion and increase of the species in the North Sea region. Recent decreases have to be treated with caution, as this may reflect displacement of colonies or incomplete coverage in combination with the above mentioned problems to assess numbers properly. For instance, the major breeding site on the island of Föhr is not completely covered annually.

In Schleswig-Holstein, also active clutch management (to prevent eggs to hatch successfully) is carried out to limit population growth, but its impact on abundance is unclear yet. The Wadden Sea breeders are part of the North Sea breeding population, which has stabilised in the past years, following major offtake of breeding birds in the Netherlands (Sørensen et al. 2025).

4.4 BARNACLE GOOSE

Overall trend in the Wadden Sea

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

No trend analysis available:
Species does not occur in this part of the Wadden Sea or is only an accidental breeder or occurs in very small numbers.

Denmark

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Lower Saxony/Hamburg

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Schleswig-Holstein

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

The Netherlands

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Trend summary: long term and short term

Area	1991-2023	2012-2023
Wadden Sea	↑↑	▬
Denmark	▬▬	▬▬
Schleswig-Holstein	▬▬	↓
Lower Saxony/Hamburg	▬▬	▬▬
The Netherlands	↑↑	↑↑

↑↑ strong increase ↑ moderate increase ▬ stable
↓↓ strong decrease ↓ moderate decrease ▬▬ uncertain

Total counts in the Wadden Sea per country in 2018

Number of breeding pairs / Area

4.5 COMMON SHELDUCK

01730 *Tadorna tadorna* Gravand / Brandgans / Bergeend

Common Shelduck *Tadorna tadorna*

breeding pairs in the Wadden Sea in 2018

Population size 2018: 6,332

Numbers of Common Shelduck have been stable on the long term, but have decreased more recently. This recent decline is well captured by the counts in Schleswig-Holstein and in the Netherlands whereas in Denmark and Lower Saxony/Hamburg the decline is of more recent date and detection of significant trends was not possible yet. At least in Lower Saxony/Hamburg numbers have gone down after 2017.

Part of the observed fluctuations at the level of individual countries is likely due to census problems, as the species is notorious difficult to survey and not all birds present do actually breed. Broods may also travel considerable distances and thus some pairs counted in the Wadden Sea may actually breed further inland. Shelduck mainly breed in rabbit holes (dune areas) and in e.g. deserted buildings (mainland) and occur widespread over the entire Wadden Sea, concentrating on the islands. Trends in numbers on the islands and along the mainland coast are very similar. ~~~

4.5 COMMON SHELDUCK

Overall trend in the Wadden Sea

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

—●— Mainland ····· Island

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Denmark

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Schleswig-Holstein

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Lower Saxony/Hamburg

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

The Netherlands

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Trend summary: long term and short term

Area	1991-2023	2012-2023
Wadden Sea	stable	strong decrease
Denmark	stable	uncertain
Schleswig-Holstein	stable	strong decrease
Lower Saxony/Hamburg	moderate increase	uncertain
The Netherlands	stable	strong decrease

↑↑ strong increase ↑ moderate increase ▬ stable
↓↓ strong decrease ↓ moderate decrease ▬▬ uncertain

Total counts in the Wadden Sea per country in 2018

Number of breeding pairs / Area

4.6 COMMON EIDER

02060 *Somateria mollissima* Ederfugl / Eiderente / Eider

Common Eider *Somateria mollissima*

breeding pairs in the Wadden Sea in 2018

Population size 2018: 5,282

The trend in Common Eider is dominated by the Netherlands, where largest part of the Wadden Sea population breeds on the islands (both dunes and salt marshes; only very few are found in the salt marshes along the mainland coast). Long-term trends have been negative, initiated by mass-starvation among wintering Eiders in 1999/2000 and attributed to depletion of mussel stocks by shellfish fisheries (e.g. Desholm et al. 2002).

In the Netherlands, recent numbers show a moderate increase, but not yet to former levels reported earlier in the 1990s. Also the smaller population in Lower/Saxony and Hamburg has increased over the past twelve years. As the species is difficult to monitor due to its breeding behaviour, some fluctuations may also reflect census problems or annual variation in the number of birds that actually breed. Currently, experiments with drones and thermal devices are carried out in order to improve counting methods and achieve more standardized count results. ~~~

4.6 COMMON EIDER

Overall trend in the Wadden Sea

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Denmark

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Lower Saxony/Hamburg

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Schleswig-Holstein

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

The Netherlands

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Trend summary: long term and short term

Area	1991-2023	2012-2023
Wadden Sea	↓	↑
Denmark	↑	—
Schleswig-Holstein	↓	—
Lower Saxony/Hamburg	↑	↑
The Netherlands	↓	—

↑ ↑ strong increase ↑ moderate increase ▬ stable
↓ ↓ strong decrease ↓ moderate decrease ▬ uncertain

Total counts in the Wadden Sea per country in 2018

Number of breeding pairs / Area

4.7 RED-BREASTED MERGANSER

02210 *Mergus serrator* Toppet Skallesluger / Mittelsäger / Middelste Zaagbek

Red-breasted Merganser *Mergus serrator*

breeding pairs in the Wadden Sea in 2018

Population size 2018: 72

Red-breasted Merganser is only breeding in small numbers in the Wadden Sea, where it reaches the southern edge of its breeding range.

Hence, large numbers especially occur in Schleswig-Holstein where the species has increased both on long and short term. This increase is in contrast with an overall decline in Germany, where largest numbers occur along the Baltic coast (Gerlach et al. 2025).

In the Netherlands and in Denmark, the species has become an accidental breeder in recent years. Larger numbers are breeding in the Rhine and Meuse Delta area, Southwest-Netherlands, where the species has also gone down recently (Boele et al. 2024).

4.7 RED-BREASTED MERGANSER

Overall trend in the Wadden Sea

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

No trend analysis available:
Species does not occur in this part of the Wadden Sea or is only an accidental breeder or occurs in very small numbers.

Denmark

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Lower Saxony/Hamburg

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Schleswig-Holstein

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

The Netherlands

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Trend summary: long term and short term

Area	1991-2023	2012-2023
Wadden Sea	↑	—
Denmark	—	—
Schleswig-Holstein	↑	↑
Lower Saxony/Hamburg	—	—
The Netherlands	↓	—

↑↑ strong increase ↑ moderate increase ▬ stable
↓↓ strong decrease ↓ moderate decrease ▬ uncertain

Total counts in the Wadden Sea per country in 2018

Number of breeding pairs / Area

4.8 HEN HARRIER

02610 *Circus cyaneus* Blå Kærhøg / Kornweihe / Blauwe Kiekendief

Hen Harrier *Circus cyaneus*

breeding pairs in the Wadden Sea in 2018

DENMARK

Schleswig-Holstein

GERMANY

Lower Saxony/
Hamburg

THE NETHERLANDS

Population size 2018: 6

Breeding Hen Harriers are mainly restricted to the Netherlands and Lower Saxony/Hamburg, where the species inhabits dune habitats on the islands, occasionally also farmland behind the seawall along the mainland coast. In Schleswig-Holstein, accidental breeders on the islands of Sylt and Amrum may have been missed during the surveys. The species has been subject to an overall decline, which started in the Netherlands in the early 2000s (e.g. van Turnhout et al. 2013), followed by a similar trend in Lower Saxony (e.g. Knipping & Stahl 2018).

Currently, the species is on the brink of extinction as a breeding bird in the Wadden Sea (and also in the Netherlands and Germany as a whole) with only few remaining breeding pairs and bleak future prospects. Elsewhere in Europe it is experiencing declines as well (Keller et al. 2020).

4.8 HEN HARRIER

Overall trend in the Wadden Sea

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Denmark

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Lower Saxony/Hamburg

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Schleswig-Holstein

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

The Netherlands

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Trend summary: long term and short term

Area	1991-2023	2012-2023
Wadden Sea	Strong decrease	Uncertain
Denmark		
Schleswig-Holstein		
Lower Saxony/Hamburg	Strong decrease	Uncertain
The Netherlands	Moderate decrease	Uncertain

↑↑ strong increase ↑ moderate increase ▬ stable
↓↓ strong decrease ↓ moderate decrease ▬ uncertain

Total counts in the Wadden Sea per country in 2018

Number of breeding pairs / Area

4.9 EURASIAN OYSTERCATCHER

04500 *Haematopus ostralegus* Strandskade / Austernfischer / Scholekster

Population size 2018: 28,694

Eurasian Oystercatcher is still one of the most abundant breeding birds in the Wadden Sea, occurring in a wide range of habitats, with highest densities on salt marshes, Hallig islands and farmland areas. It has been subject to ongoing declines all over the Wadden Sea, especially after the early 2000s. The current population level in the Wadden Sea is less than 50% of the level in the 1990s, as a result of a 3%-annual-decline since 1991.

There are no pronounced differences in trends within the Wadden Sea, nor between mainland breeding areas and breeding areas on the islands. The latter may be surprising, as island populations usually experience lower predation rates compared to the mainland coast (but see for Hallig islands below). In Schleswig-Holstein and in the Netherlands, recent trends have remained stable on a low level.

The observed decline is likely caused by low breeding success, as shown by data from the TMAP parameter breeding success (Koffijberg et al. in prep.), which in turn is at least a result of high predation risk and increased flooding (van de Pol et al. 2010, Bailey et al. 2011, van de Pol et al. 2024). Especially on the Hallig islands in Schleswig-Holstein, heavy predation by Brown rat has been reported for multiple years, leading to almost complete breeding failures (e.g. Gnep et al. 2021).

Furthermore, food limitations in winter have been discussed as well as a factor causing numbers to decline (e.g. Allen et al. 2019). Also wintering numbers in the Wadden Sea have gone down considerably (Kleefstra et al. 2025).

4.9 EURASIAN OYSTERCATCHER

Overall trend in the Wadden Sea

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

—●— Mainland - - - ● - - - Island

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Trend summary: long term and short term

Area	1991-2023	2012-2023
Wadden Sea	↓	↓
Denmark	↓	↓
Schleswig-Holstein	↓	▬
Lower Saxony/Hamburg	↓	↓
The Netherlands	↓	▬

↑ ↑ strong increase ↑ moderate increase ▬ stable
↓ ↓ strong decrease ↓ moderate decrease ▬ uncertain

Denmark

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Schleswig-Holstein

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Total counts in the Wadden Sea per country in 2018

Number of breeding pairs / Area

Lower Saxony/Hamburg

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

The Netherlands

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

4.10 PIED AVOCET

04560 *Recurvirostra avoetia* Klyde / Säbelschnäbler / Kluut

Pied Avocet *Recurvirostra avoetia*

breeding pairs in the Wadden Sea in 2018

Population size 2018: 6,700

Avocet is one of the prime breeding bird species in the Wadden Sea, also supporting a relevant share of the Northwest-European breeding population. Like Eurasian Oystercatcher, the species has declined on a long term, especially after the early 2000s (Denmark, the Netherlands) and late 2000s (Schleswig-Holstein).

In Lower Saxony/Hamburg, signs of a decline became apparent already in the mid-1990s. Declines have persisted in the recent decade, apart from a stabilisation in the Netherlands. Due to its preference for silty mud flats, Pied Avocet mainly breeds on the mainland coast, where they locally suffer from high predation rates caused by mammalian predators.

Locally, larger concentrations also breed in coastal wetlands, also susceptible to high predation risk, and therefore often breeding at sites protected by electric fences. Besides, the species is vulnerable to cold and stormy weather in the chick-rearing period in May and June, affecting chick survival. Data from the TMAP parameter breeding success point at persistent low breeding success all over the Wadden Sea (Koffijberg et al. in prep.), which is likely a main driver for the observed decline in breeding numbers. Causes for failure may be associated with high predation rates, flooding or other adverse weather conditions. ~~~~

4.10 PIED AVOCET

Overall trend in the Wadden Sea

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Denmark

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Lower Saxony/Hamburg

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Schleswig-Holstein

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

The Netherlands

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Trend summary: long term and short term

Area	1991-2023	2012-2023
Wadden Sea	↓ ↓	↓
Denmark	↓ ↓	— —
Schleswig-Holstein	↓ ↓	— —
Lower Saxony/Hamburg	↓ ↓	↓
The Netherlands	↓ ↓	▬

↑ ↑ strong increase ↑ moderate increase ▬ stable
↓ ↓ strong decrease ↓ moderate decrease — — uncertain

Total counts in the Wadden Sea per country in 2018

Number of breeding pairs / Area

4.11 COMMON RINGED PLOVER

04700 *Charadrius hiaticula* Stor Præstekrave / Sandregenpfeifer / Bontbekplevier

Common Ringed Plover *Charadrius hiaticula*

breeding pairs in the Wadden Sea in 2018

Population size 2018: 777

Common Ringed Plover is among the most declining breeding bird species in the Wadden Sea. It has shown downward trends in all sections of the Wadden Sea and the rate of annual decrease (~4% per year) is very similar in the individual countries, indicating that factors causing the decline may operate at larger scale.

Over the past years, numbers fluctuate (Schleswig-Holstein, the Netherlands) or have remained stable at a low level (Lower Saxony/Hamburg). Only in Denmark, there have been some signs of recovery after 2015 (cf. Kentish Plover), but this has not persisted until the end of the data series. Hence, all trends for the past twelve years remain uncertain. Some of the fluctuations in the trend may also be associated with the species' mobile dispersal, since in most countries only a selection of sites is monitored for the species (preferably in future monitoring, all breeding sites should be included).

Ringed Plovers may use natural habitats on beaches (often protected to avoid public access), sand bars and lower dunes, but also breed on more artificial sites on large parking lots or in port areas, when these offer suitable and undisturbed breeding habitat. Beach breeders locally have suffered frequent flooding by summer storms or have faced problems with sand drift caused by stormy weather while incubating. Trends at mainland breeding sites and islands are very similar and both fit well in the overall Wadden Sea trend. The species is subject to various dedicated conservation programmes in all Wadden Sea countries (e.g. Cimiotti & Altemüller 2022 for Schleswig-Holstein).

4.11 COMMON RINGED PLOVER

Overall trend in the Wadden Sea

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

—●— Mainland ····· Island

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Trend summary: long term and short term

Area	1991-2023	2012-2023
Wadden Sea	↓	— —
Denmark	↓	— —
Schleswig-Holstein	↓	— —
Lower Saxony/Hamburg	↓	— —
The Netherlands	↓	■

↑↑ strong increase ↑ moderate increase ■ stable
↓↓ strong decrease ↓ moderate decrease — — uncertain

Denmark

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Schleswig-Holstein

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Total counts in the Wadden Sea per country in 2018

Number of breeding pairs / Area

Lower Saxony/Hamburg

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

The Netherlands

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

4.12 KENTISH PLOVER

04770 *Charadrius alexandrinus* Hvidbrystet Præstekrave / Seeregenpfeifer / Strandplevier

Kentish Plover *Charadrius alexandrinus*

breeding pairs in the Wadden Sea in 2018

Population size 2018: 435

The Wadden Sea represents one of the core breeding areas for Kentish Plover in Northwest-Europe. The long-term negative trend in the Wadden Sea was most pronounced in the Netherlands and Lower Saxony/Hamburg where the species merely has become an accidental breeder in the past decade.

In Denmark it has even increased both over long- and short term whereas the relatively large population breeding in mainly coastal wetlands (e.g. Beltringharder Koog, Klinner-Hötker et al. 2021) in Schleswig-Holstein has remained stable over time.

It is mainly the situation in Denmark that also dominates an increasing trend at the Wadden Sea islands (especially Rømø). Here, as well as in Schleswig-Holstein, the species benefits from specific measures like fencing (to reduce predation risk) to facilitate successful breeding. Similar to Common Ringed Plover, beach breeding spots are mostly protected to avoid easy public access. ~~~

4.12 KENTISH PLOVER

Overall trend in the Wadden Sea

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

—●— Mainland ····· Island

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Denmark

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Schleswig-Holstein

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Lower Saxony/Hamburg

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

The Netherlands

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Trend summary: long term and short term

Area	1991-2023	2012-2023
Wadden Sea	↓	—
Denmark	↑	↑
Schleswig-Holstein	▬	▬
Lower Saxony/Hamburg	↓↓	—
The Netherlands	↓↓	—

↑↑ strong increase ↑ moderate increase ▬ stable
↓↓ strong decrease ↓ moderate decrease — uncertain

Total counts in the Wadden Sea per country in 2018

Number of breeding pairs / Area

4.13 NORTHERN LAPWING

04930 *Vanellus vanellus* Vibe / Kiebitz / Kievit

Northern Lapwing *Vanellus vanellus*

breeding pairs in the Wadden Sea in 2018

Population size 2018: 11,194

Northern Lapwing has been subject to an ongoing decline in the Wadden Sea, with an average decrease of 2% per year since 1991. The population remained stable over a long time in the Dutch part of the Wadden Sea (in contrast to losses in farmland areas in the interior parts of the country), but started to go down as well after 2010, resulting in an overall long term decline.

For the last twelve years, overall Wadden Sea numbers have stabilised at a lower level, but have continued to decrease in the Netherlands (-3% per year since 2012) (trends in other countries in this period uncertain).

Mainland and island trends are very similar, although the decline started about ten years earlier on the islands. From 2019 onwards numbers at the islands show some sign of recovery. Preferred habitat is open grassland, both behind the seawall and on salt marshes with some degree of agricultural management (e.g. livestock grazing).

4.13 NORTHERN LAPWING

Overall trend in the Wadden Sea

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

—●— Mainland ····· Island

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Trend summary: long term and short term

Area	1991-2023	2012-2023
Wadden Sea	↓	▬
Denmark	↓	▬▬
Schleswig-Holstein	↓	▬▬
Lower Saxony/Hamburg	↓	▬▬
The Netherlands	↓	↓

↑↑ strong increase ↑ moderate increase ▬ stable
↓↓ strong decrease ↓ moderate decrease ▬▬ uncertain

Denmark

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Schleswig-Holstein

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Total counts in the Wadden Sea per country in 2018

Number of breeding pairs / Area

Lower Saxony/Hamburg

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

The Netherlands

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

4.14 BLACK-TAILED GODWIT

05320 *Limosa limosa* Stor Kobbbersneppe / Uferschnepfe / Grutto

Black-tailed Godwit

Limosa limosa

breeding pairs in the Wadden Sea in 2018

Population size 2018: 2,160

Breeding Black-tailed Godwits in the Wadden Sea are mainly found in coastal grasslands behind the seawall, in coastal wetlands, summer polders and salt marshes.

The overall Wadden Sea trend has been negative, reflected well in trends in abundance for Denmark, Lower Saxony/Hamburg and the Netherlands. In Schleswig-Holstein there was an initial increase in some coastal areas in the 1990s, after abandonment of active management (Eskildsen et al. 2000, Hälterlein et al. 2003) but this development did not sustain and was followed by a decline after 2000.

Since 2012 overall numbers have fluctuated at a low level; only in the Netherlands a significant decline has continued until recently. Mainland and island areas have similar trends, apart from the fact that population level at the islands has remained at a higher level and along the mainland coast these have stabilised at lower levels during the last twelve years. In future trend analyses it would be desirable when a larger set of census areas could be included, so trends reflect local developments better and provide an overall more robust assessment.

4.14 BLACK-TAILED GODWIT

Overall trend in the Wadden Sea

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

—●— Mainland ·····●···· Island

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Denmark

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Schleswig-Holstein

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Lower Saxony/Hamburg

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

The Netherlands

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Trend summary: long term and short term

Area	1991-2023	2012-2023
Wadden Sea	↓	— —
Denmark	↓	— —
Schleswig-Holstein	— —	— —
Lower Saxony/Hamburg	↓	— —
The Netherlands	↓	↓

↑ ↑ strong increase ↑ moderate increase ▬ stable
↓ ↓ strong decrease ↓ moderate decrease — — uncertain

Total counts in the Wadden Sea per country in 2018

Number of breeding pairs / Area

4.15 EURASIAN CURLEW

05410 *Numenius arquata* Storspove / Großer Brachvogel / Wulp

Eurasian Curlew *Numenius arquata*

breeding pairs in the Wadden Sea in 2018

Population size 2018: 355

Eurasian Curlew is a typical dune-breeding species in the Wadden Sea. Hence, it is mainly confined to the islands, especially those west of the River Elbe, in the Netherlands and Lower-Saxony. The species is in decline, mainly due to losses in the Netherlands, where highest densities occur and where the species has experienced a long-term decline with on average 3% per year (-5% per year since 2012).

This development has been attributed to management (negative response to livestock grazing) and vegetation succession in coastal dunes and is especially resulting from low chick survival (Kleefstra et al. 2021), hinting at limited food resources as well. In Lower Saxony/Hamburg (but mainly Lower Saxony) the long-term trend has remained stable.

4.15 EURASIAN CURLEW

Overall trend in the Wadden Sea

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Denmark

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Lower Saxony/Hamburg

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

No trend analysis available:
Species does not occur in this part of the Wadden Sea or is only an accidental breeder or occurs in very small numbers.

Schleswig-Holstein

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

The Netherlands

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Trend summary: long term and short term

Area	1991-2023	2012-2023
Wadden Sea	↓	↓
Denmark	—	—
Schleswig-Holstein		
Lower Saxony/Hamburg	—	—
The Netherlands	↓	↓

↑ ↑ strong increase ↑ moderate increase — stable
↓ ↓ strong decrease ↓ moderate decrease — uncertain

Total counts in the Wadden Sea per country in 2018

Number of breeding pairs / Area

4.16 COMMON REDSHANK

05460 *Tringa totanus* Rødben / Rotschenkel / Tureluur

Common Redshank *Tringa totanus*

breeding pairs in the Wadden Sea in 2018

Population size 2018: 12,537

Common Redshank is an abundant breeder in naturally and semi-naturally structured salt marsh areas with patchy vegetation, often associated with low-intensity management regimes. Locally, high densities may occur, which also come with some difficulties to assess their abundance. Besides, the species also inhabits grasslands behind the seawall, but usually in lower densities compared to salt marshes.

The overall Wadden Sea numbers have gradually declined with 1% per year since 1991 and this trend has become apparent especially after 2000. An exception is Schleswig-Holstein, where stable numbers have been reported for the entire data series 1991-2023 (including some fluctuations which do not affect the overall trend). Initial declines in Denmark and the Netherlands have stabilised in the past twelve years.

In Lower-Saxony/Hamburg, where the entire data series 1991-2023 suggests a moderate decline, the twelve-year trend was uncertain. Trends for mainland and island breeding sites are very similar, apart from some larger fluctuations at the islands and an overall higher population level at island breeding sites in the past decade.

4.16 COMMON REDSHANK

Overall trend in the Wadden Sea

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

—●— Mainland ····· Island

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Denmark

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Schleswig-Holstein

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Lower Saxony/Hamburg

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

The Netherlands

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Trend summary: long term and short term

Area	1991-2023	2012-2023
Wadden Sea	↓	▬
Denmark	↓	▬
Schleswig-Holstein	▬	▬
Lower Saxony/Hamburg	↓	▬▬
The Netherlands	↓	▬

↑↑ strong increase ↑ moderate increase ▬ stable
↓↓ strong decrease ↓ moderate decrease ▬▬ uncertain

Total counts in the Wadden Sea per country in 2018

Number of breeding pairs / Area

4.17 MEDITERRANEAN GULL

05750 *Larus melanocephalus* Sorthovedet Måge / Schwarzkopfmöwe / Zwartkopmeeuw

Mediterranean Gull *Ichthyaetus melanocephalus*

breeding pairs in the Wadden Sea in 2018

Population size 2018: 35

Mediterranean Gull has expanded its breeding range in Northwest-Europe considerably in the past decades (Keller et al. 2020) and has also colonised the Wadden Sea. In 1991 the species was only found in the Netherlands, in 1992 it settled in Schleswig-Holstein, followed by Lower Saxony/Hamburg in 1994 and Denmark in 1996.

The overall Wadden Sea trend does not show a consistent pattern, apart from a very recent increase which has become apparent in Schleswig-Holstein, Lower Saxony/Hamburg and the Netherlands. Only in Lower Saxony/Hamburg this resulted in a clear moderate increase for the last twelve years.

Settlement of Mediterranean Gulls within the Wadden Sea may be erratic and opportunistic, often also associated with local occurrence of Black-headed Gulls and Common Gulls, or as a result of colonies being raided by mammalian predators, as occurred just outside the Wadden Sea along the River Elbe (Koffijberg et al. 2020) (the numbers at these sites were formerly included in the progress reports but being outside the Wadden Sea Cooperation area, and therefore have now been excluded). In the hinterland of the Wadden Sea and some urban sites (e.g. in Hamburg; Garthe et al. 2025), increases have been more pronounced. In the Netherlands, 89% of the population is breeding in the Delta area, Southwest-Netherlands (Boele et al. 2025).

4.17 MEDITERRANEAN GULL

Overall trend in the Wadden Sea

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

No trend analysis available:
Species does not occur in this part of the Wadden Sea or is only an accidental breeder or occurs in very small numbers.

Denmark

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Schleswig-Holstein

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Lower Saxony/Hamburg

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

The Netherlands

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Trend summary: long term and short term

Area	1991-2023	2012-2023
Wadden Sea	— —	— —
Denmark		
Schleswig-Holstein	↑	— —
Lower Saxony/Hamburg	↑ ↑	↑
The Netherlands	↑	— —

↑↑ strong increase ↑ moderate increase — stable
↓↓ strong decrease ↓ moderate decrease — — uncertain

Total counts in the Wadden Sea per country in 2018

Number of breeding pairs / Area

4.18 COMMON BLACK-HEADED GULL

05820 *Chroicocephalus ridibundus* Hættemåge / Lachmöwe / Kokmeeuw

Black-headed Gull *Chroicocephalus ridibundus*

breeding pairs in the Wadden Sea in 2018

Population size 2018: 83,071

Black-headed Gull is one of the most abundant breeding birds in the Wadden Sea. Large colonies are especially situated in salt marshes, on remote islands and locally also in coastal wetlands. Predation risk (notably along the mainland coast) or deteriorating habitat may cause displacements to other (safe) breeding sites, as has been observed in the eastern part of the Dutch part of the Wadden Sea (e.g. Manche et al. 2025) and is suspected for Denmark (see below). Overall Wadden Sea numbers remained stable until 2001 but have experienced a decline since then, resulting in a downward long-term trend of -2% per year. Trends in Lower Saxony/Hamburg and in the Netherlands are highly similar, also regarding the onset of the decline in 2001. Perhaps the reasons for the observed decline may (also) be associated with large-scale environmental changes (e.g. affecting food resources) rather than local developments like increased predation risk. In contrast, colonies in Schleswig-Holstein and Denmark have shown mixed fortunes. In Denmark there has been a significant long-term increase, which is mainly attributed to the expansion of a single colony in Sneum Digesø near Sneum Sluse, which may have received breeders from other colonies in the wider region as well. However, such a concentration makes the species very susceptible to 'freak events', like the outbreak of highly pathogenic avian influenza in 2023 (Hälterlein 2023, Garthe & Kubetzki 2025). In Schleswig-Holstein numbers have remained stable, though with some fluctuations and thus resulting in an uncertain twelve-year trend. For the last twelve years, the overall Wadden Sea trend has stabilised at a lower level. Only in the Netherlands, declines have continued. Here, results from the breeding success monitoring scheme point at low productivity in most years (Koffijberg et al. 2021).

4.18 COMMON BLACK-HEADED GULL

Overall trend in the Wadden Sea

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

— Mainland ··· Island

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Trend summary: long term and short term

Area	1991-2023	2012-2023
Wadden Sea	↓	▬
Denmark	↑	▬▬
Schleswig-Holstein	▬	▬▬
Lower Saxony/Hamburg	↓	▬▬
The Netherlands	↓	↓

↑↑ strong increase ↑ moderate increase ▬ stable
↓↓ strong decrease ↓ moderate decrease ▬▬ uncertain

Denmark

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Schleswig-Holstein

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Total counts in the Wadden Sea per country in 2018

Number of breeding pairs / Area

Lower Saxony/Hamburg

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

The Netherlands

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

4.19 COMMON GULL

05900 *Larus canus* Stormmålge / Sturmmöwe / Stormmeeuw

Common Gull

Larus canus

breeding pairs in the Wadden Sea in 2018

Population size 2018: 8,773

In the 1990s, the Common Gull was a thriving species in the Wadden Sea, especially as a result from increases in Schleswig-Holstein and Lower Saxony/Hamburg (stable numbers in the Netherlands, only very small numbers in Denmark, no trend calculation possible). However, in the early 2000s, numbers started to decrease, most pronounced in the Netherlands but also apparent in Lower Saxony/Hamburg after 2016. Overall this results in a long-term decrease (-1% per year), which has accelerated over the past twelve years (-7% per year).

In Schleswig-Holstein, the situation differs from the Western Wadden Sea. After the initial increase in the 1990s, numbers remained at a fairly stable level, also resulting in a stable trend over the last twelve years. Earlier, it has been hypothesised that the increase in the Schleswig-Holstein part of the Wadden Sea was associated with displacements from colonies in the Baltic (e.g. Garthe et al. 2000).

The current stable trend in Schleswig-Holstein contrasts with an overall decrease in Germany in the past twelve years (Gerlach et al. 2025) while in the Netherlands, the Wadden Sea trend fits well in the overall decline reported elsewhere in the country (Boele et al. 2025). Drivers for these mixed trends are unclear.

4.19 COMMON GULL

Overall trend in the Wadden Sea

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Denmark

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Lower Saxony/Hamburg

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Schleswig-Holstein

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

The Netherlands

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Trend summary: long term and short term

Area	1991-2023	2012-2023
Wadden Sea	↓ ↓	↓ ↓ ↓
Denmark	↓	↓ ↓ ↓
Schleswig-Holstein	↑	▬
Lower Saxony/Hamburg	↑	↓ ↓ ↓
The Netherlands	↓	↓

↑ ↑ strong increase
 ↑ moderate increase
 ▬ stable
↓ ↓ strong decrease
 ↓ moderate decrease
▬ uncertain

Total counts in the Wadden Sea per country in 2018

Number of breeding pairs / Area

4.20 LESSER BLACK-BACKED GULL

05910 *Larus fuscus* Sildemåge / Heringsmöwe / Kleine Mantelmeeuw

Great Black-backed Gull *Larus marinus*

breeding pairs in the Wadden Sea in 2018

Population size 2018: 71,838

In the early days of the trilateral breeding bird monitoring scheme, the Lesser Black-backed Gull was among the fastest expanding species in the Wadden Sea. Still, long-term trends point at increases in all sections of the Wadden Sea, where colonies are mainly situated in large dune areas on the islands. However, the situation has changed more recently. At the scale of the Wadden Sea, this upward trend started to level off in 2007 and this pattern is basically similar in Schleswig-Holstein, Lower Saxony/Hamburg and in the Netherlands (much smaller numbers in Denmark increased until 2013).

Apart from Lower Saxony/Hamburg, where numbers remained stable at high level, numbers breeding in Schleswig-Holstein and in the Netherlands significantly went down over the past twelve years, in the Netherlands even with a 4%-decrease annually. The small Danish population showed a reversed trend with numbers in 2023 at about the same level as in the early 2000s

The saturation or even regional declines are likely associated with low reproductive output and limitations in marine food supplies, also as a result of changed fisheries discard regulations (e.g. Camphuysen 2013) and they also come with increased feeding in inland areas.

In many parts of Europe, the species has also successfully colonised inland breeding sites (Keller et al. 2020), even in urban areas and on rooftops in large industrial estates (e.g. van Turnhout et al. 2023).

4.20 LESSER BLACK-BACKED GULL

Overall trend in the Wadden Sea

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Denmark

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Schleswig-Holstein

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Lower Saxony/Hamburg

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

The Netherlands

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Trend summary: long term and short term

Area	1991-2023	2012-2023
Wadden Sea	↑	↓
Denmark	↑↑	↓↓
Schleswig-Holstein	↑	↓
Lower Saxony/Hamburg	↑	▬
The Netherlands	↑	↓

↑↑ strong increase ↑ moderate increase ▬ stable
↓↓ strong decrease ↓ moderate decrease ■ uncertain

Total counts in the Wadden Sea per country in 2018

Number of breeding pairs / Area

4.21 HERRING GULL

05920 *Larus argentatus* Sølvmåge / Silbermöwe / Zilvermeeuw

Herring Gull *Larus argentatus*

breeding pairs in the Wadden Sea in 2018

Population size 2018: 42,526

Contrary to the Lesser Black-backed Gull, the Herring Gull has shown ongoing declines since the start of the trilateral monitoring in 1991. Before that, the species had increased (or merely recovered) in the 1970s and 1980s, after losses by human intervention in earlier decades. Overall, the negative trend had a rate of -3% per year since 1991.

Long-term trends in the Netherlands and in Lower Saxony/Hamburg have many similarities, whereas in Schleswig-Holstein the rate of decline was slower and the trend has even stabilised over the past twelve years.

Further studies with help of ringed birds could reveal if these regional differences are associated with productivity and/or survival probability and recruitment (cf. Kentie et al. 2022). Only the smaller population in Denmark has been thriving for a long time, but tends to decline as well in more recent years. Similar to Lesser Black-backed Gull, declines have been attributed to low breeding success, caused by limitations in food resources (e.g. Camphuysen 2013).

In addition, several studies have also pointed at lower survival probabilities in the past decades (van der Jeugd et al. 2024, Camphuysen 2013, Kentie et al. 2022), being a major driver for population declines. Largest colonies in the Wadden Sea are situated in dune areas on the islands, often in mixed-colonies with Lesser Black-backed Gull.

4.21 HERRING GULL

Overall trend in the Wadden Sea

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Denmark

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Schleswig-Holstein

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Lower Saxony/Hamburg

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

The Netherlands

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Trend summary: long term and short term

Area	1991-2023	2012-2023
Wadden Sea	↓	↓
Denmark	↑	—
Schleswig-Holstein	↓	—
Lower Saxony/Hamburg	↓	—
The Netherlands	↓	↓

↑↑ strong increase ↑ moderate increase — stable
↓↓ strong decrease ↓ moderate decrease — uncertain

Total counts in the Wadden Sea per country in 2018

Number of breeding pairs / Area

4.22 GREAT BLACK-BACKED GULL

06000 *Larus marinus* Svartbag / Mantelmöwe / Grote Mantelmeeuw

Great Black-backed Gull *Larus marinus*

breeding pairs in the Wadden Sea in 2018

Population size 2018: 171

Contrary to global developments (Langlois Lopez et al. 2022), the Great Black-backed Gull has expanded its breeding range in Southwestern direction into the Wadden Sea. Especially after 2010, increases were captured by counts in Schleswig-Holstein (holding the largest numbers) and in the Netherlands, to a lesser extent also in Denmark and in Lower Saxony/Hamburg.

The overall Wadden Sea trend since 1991 shows an 11%-increase per year, slightly accelerated after 2012 (+13%). It is actually one of the very few breeding birds showing a pronounced increase. Still, the species may be difficult to find and numbers biased low, as it often breeds scattered in large colonies of Herring- and Lesser Black-backed Gulls on the Wadden Sea islands and thus may remain undetected during some surveys. ~~~

4.22 GREAT BLACK-BACKED GULL

Overall trend in the Wadden Sea

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Denmark

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Schleswig-Holstein

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Lower Saxony/Hamburg

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

The Netherlands

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Trend summary: long term and short term

Area	1991-2023	2012-2023
Wadden Sea	↑↑	↑↑
Denmark	↑	—
Schleswig-Holstein	↑↑	↑↑
Lower Saxony/Hamburg	↑	↑
The Netherlands	—	↑↑

↑↑ strong increase ↑ moderate increase — stable
↓↓ strong decrease ↓ moderate decrease — uncertain

Total counts in the Wadden Sea per country in 2018

Number of breeding pairs / Area

4.23 GULL-BILLED TERN

06050 *Gelochelidon nilotica* Sandterne / Lachseeschwalbe / Lachstern

Gull-billed Tern *Gelochelidon nilotica*

breeding pairs in the Wadden Sea in 2018

Population size 2018: 37

The Wadden Sea harbours the only breeding area for Gull-billed Terns in Northwest-Europe. In earlier decades, breeding was confined to Denmark, but since the 1970s this has shifted to Schleswig-Holstein, where the species is currently breeding in a colony in Neufelderkoog in the Elbe estuary, associated with Black-headed Gull, Common Tern and Arctic Tern.

Earlier short-term settlements in the Lower Saxon part of the Elbe estuary have been deserted. In the Netherlands, only accidental breeding (attempts) has been reported (2005, 2020), partly outside the Wadden Sea. Current numbers at Neufelderkoog are somewhat lower than in the beginning of the trilateral monitoring, but recent numbers are very stable. The species is monitored by an intensive surveillance programme and the breeding site is protected by specific measures like fences (Risch et al. 2018, see also <https://gelochelidon.de/>).

4.23 GULL-BILLED TERN

Overall trend in the Wadden Sea

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Denmark

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Schleswig-Holstein

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

The Netherlands

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Lower Saxony/Hamburg

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Trend summary: long term and short term

Area	1991-2023	2012-2023
Wadden Sea	▬	▬▬
Denmark		
Schleswig-Holstein	↑	▬▬
Lower Saxony/Hamburg		
The Netherlands		

↑↑ strong increase ↑ moderate increase ▬ stable
↓↓ strong decrease ↓ moderate decrease ▬▬ uncertain

Total counts in the Wadden Sea per country in 2018

Number of breeding pairs / Area

4.24 SANDWICH TERN

06110 *Thalasseus sandvicensis* Splitterne / Brandseeschwalbe / Grote Stern

Sandwich Tern *Thalasseus sandvicensis*

breeding pairs in the Wadden Sea in 2018

Population size 2018: 16,035

Colonies of Sandwich Tern in the Wadden Sea represent a large part of the Northwest-European breeding population. Until recently, the species used to breed mainly on remote islands like Griend (the Netherlands) and Norderoog (Schleswig-Holstein) and its long-term trend is classified as stable. Local variations include a long-term decline in Schleswig-Holstein and highly fluctuating (and small numbers; 2023 absent) in Denmark.

However, the situation for the species has changed dramatically in recent years. The drop in numbers in 2023 expresses the impact of outbreaks of highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI), which started 2022 (e.g. El-Hacen 2022, Pohlmann et al. 2023) and had a profound impact on all breeding colonies in Northwest-Europe, with a loss of more than 17% of the total breeding population (Knief et al. 2024). Besides the impact of HPAI, the colony at Norderoog in Schleswig-Holstein has also suffered from high predation rates by Brown rat (*B. Gnep*, V. Hennig).

Currently, both large colonies mentioned above have been abandoned by the species, and settlements at other sites show considerable dynamics. In the Dutch part of the Wadden Sea, also raids of large gulls (often immature, notably Great Black-backed Gull) have caused abandonment of colonies as well, for instance on the island of Ameland and more recently also colonies at the island of Texel (Boele et al. 2025).

4.24 SANDWICH TERN

Overall trend in the Wadden Sea

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Denmark

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Lower Saxony/Hamburg

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Schleswig-Holstein

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

The Netherlands

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Trend summary: long term and short term

Area	1991-2023	2012-2023
Wadden Sea	▬	▬▬
Denmark	▬▬	▬▬
Schleswig-Holstein	↓	↑
Lower Saxony/Hamburg	▬▬	▬▬
The Netherlands	▬	▬▬

↑↑ strong increase ↑ moderate increase ▬ stable
↓↓ strong decrease ↓ moderate decrease ▬▬ uncertain

Total counts in the Wadden Sea per country in 2018

Number of breeding pairs / Area

4.25 COMMON TERN

06150 *Sterna hirundo* Fjordterne / Flusseeeschwalbe / Visdief

Common Tern *Sterna hirundo*

breeding pairs in the Wadden Sea in 2018

Population size 2018: 7,198

Breeding Common Terns are widespread in the Wadden Sea and inhabit different habitats, including port areas, rooftops of buildings and other anthropogenic habitats, including dedicated breeding platforms in Lauwersoog in the Netherlands and Esbjerg in Denmark.

Overall numbers have gone down since the very start of the trilateral monitoring, with a rate of -3% per year. Denmark and especially Schleswig-Holstein are exceptions to this development with an overall stable trend (in Denmark only small numbers involved). Most pronounced declines occurred in the large colonies in the Netherlands (-5% per year since 1991). In all parts of the Wadden Sea, no significant trends could be detected for the last twelve years.

Interestingly, numbers breeding along the mainland coast have remained stable over time (both long- and short-term trends) whereas colonies situated at islands significantly went down in numbers on the long term (last twelve years uncertain). Locally, numbers show highly dynamic settlement patterns and presumed exchange between colonies, as shown for the new breeding site 'Stern' in the Ems estuary in Groningen, the Netherlands, which quickly went up to a maximum of more than 1,400 pairs within only four years after the island was created (de Boer 2024). Like Sandwich Tern, the Common Tern suffered from recent outbreaks of HPAI as well (e.g. Pohlmann et al. 2023), but its general impact seems less profound compared to Sandwich Tern. Many breeding sites report low productivity, which may also be one of the main drivers for the observed decline.

4.25 COMMON TERN

Overall trend in the Wadden Sea

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

—●— Mainland ····· Island

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Denmark

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Schleswig-Holstein

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Lower Saxony/Hamburg

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

The Netherlands

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Trend summary: long term and short term

Area	1991-2023	2012-2023
Wadden Sea	↓	— —
Denmark	—	— —
Schleswig-Holstein	—	— —
Lower Saxony/Hamburg	↓	— —
The Netherlands	↓	— —

↑↑ strong increase ↑ moderate increase — stable
↓↓ strong decrease ↓ moderate decrease — — uncertain

Total counts in the Wadden Sea per country in 2018

Number of breeding pairs / Area

4.26 ARCTIC TERN

06160 *Sterna paradisaea* Havterne / Küstenseeschwalbe / Noordse Stern

Arctic Tern *Sterna paradisaea*

breeding pairs in the Wadden Sea in 2018

Population size 2018: 4,325

Numbers of the Arctic Tern overall remained fairly stable throughout the 1990s, but started to decrease from 1998 onwards. This pattern, with some variation, emerged in all sections of the Wadden Sea. The overall downward trend proceeded with a rate of -4% per year. Only for Denmark, Schleswig-Holstein and Lower Saxony/Hamburg no significant trends could be detected for the last twelve years while in the Netherlands ongoing declines were observed.

Trends on islands and mainland are very similar, apart from an earlier onset of decrease at mainland colony sites. Compared to Common Tern (which it sometimes associates with), Arctic Tern prefers more sparsely vegetated breeding sites and are found less in anthropogenic habitats. Often, reproductive output is low and due to its habitat preference, the species is even more susceptible to flooding during the breeding season. ~~~~

4.26 ARCTIC TERN

Overall trend in the Wadden Sea

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

—●— Mainland ····· Island

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Denmark

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Schleswig-Holstein

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Lower Saxony/Hamburg

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

The Netherlands

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Trend summary: long term and short term

Area	1991-2023	2012-2023
Wadden Sea	↓	↓
Denmark	↓	— —
Schleswig-Holstein	↓	— —
Lower Saxony/Hamburg	↓	— —
The Netherlands	↓	↓

↑↑ strong increase ↑ moderate increase ▬ stable
↓↓ strong decrease ↓ moderate decrease — — uncertain

Total counts in the Wadden Sea per country in 2018

Number of breeding pairs / Area

4.27 LITTLE TERN

06240 *Sternula albifrons* Dværgterne / Zwergseeschwalbe / Dwergstern

Little Tern *Sternula albifrons*

breeding pairs in the Wadden Sea in 2018

Population size 2018: 1,052

The Little Tern predominantly breeds on the islands, where it inhabits beaches, sand pits and primary dunes. Colony settlement may be highly dynamic, depending on flooding events and access of public to preferred beach stretches.

All over the Wadden Sea, much effort is done to keep colonies undisturbed from the public, but due to the dynamic settlement and easy displacement after e.g. flooding events, this may be challenging. Flooding is one main cause for breeding failure, but often the birds quickly start breeding again at a new site.

The dynamic settlement behaviour is also expressed by some of the regional trends, but overall the species has experienced a moderate increase (+1% per year since 1991). This is mainly driven by the developments in the Netherlands (taking the largest share in the Wadden Sea breeding population) whereas in Schleswig-Holstein and Lower Saxony/Hamburg significant negative long-term trends prevail (Denmark stable). Also, both Denmark and the Netherlands have shown increases over the past twelve years, which contrasts with Schleswig-Holstein and Lower Saxony/Hamburg, where the recent development remains uncertain. Initial increases in Lower Saxony/Hamburg in 2016-2022 were followed by a marked decrease in 2023.

4.27 LITTLE TERN

Overall trend in the Wadden Sea

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Denmark

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Lower Saxony/Hamburg

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Schleswig-Holstein

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

The Netherlands

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Trend summary: long term and short term

Area	1991-2023	2012-2023
Wadden Sea	↑	↑
Denmark	▬	↑
Schleswig-Holstein	↓	▬▬
Lower Saxony/Hamburg	↓	▬▬
The Netherlands	↑	↑

↑↑ strong increase ↑ moderate increase ▬ stable
↓↓ strong decrease ↓ moderate decrease ▬▬ uncertain

Total counts in the Wadden Sea per country in 2018

Number of breeding pairs / Area

4.28 SHORT-EARED OWL

07680 *Asio flammeus* Mosehornugl / Sumpfohreule / Velduil

Short-eared Owl

Asio ammeus

breeding pairs in the Wadden Sea in 2018

Population size 2018: 32

Short-eared Owls prefer open dunes and heathland as breeding habitat, often in association with feeding areas in grassland or salt marshes. It has its strongholds west of the River Elbe and its distribution is mainly confined to the islands, with some strongholds on the East-Frisian islands in Lower Saxony (Kämpfer et al. 2023).

Numbers usually fluctuate and partly show synchronous peaks throughout the Wadden Sea (e.g. peak year 2023), in association with years with high abundance of voles. However, the overall trend is negative especially due to the declines in the Netherlands, and more recently also in Lower Saxony/Hamburg. This trend is shared with Hen Harrier, breeding (or having bred) on the very same islands.

4.28 SHORT-EARED OWL

Overall trend in the Wadden Sea

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

No trend analysis available: Species does not occur in this part of the Wadden Sea or is only an accidental breeder or occurs in very small numbers.

Denmark

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

No trend analysis available: Species does not occur in this part of the Wadden Sea or is only an accidental breeder or occurs in very small numbers.

Schleswig-Holstein

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Lower Saxony/Hamburg

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

The Netherlands

Index (1996 = 100) / Year

Trend summary: long term and short term

Area	1991-2023	2012-2023
Wadden Sea	↓	↓
Denmark		
Schleswig-Holstein		
Lower Saxony/Hamburg	↓	▬▬
The Netherlands	↓	↓

↑↑ strong increase ↑ moderate increase ▬ stable
↓↓ strong decrease ↓ moderate decrease ▬▬ uncertain

Total counts in the Wadden Sea per country in 2018

Number of breeding pairs / Area

5. REFERENCES

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